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SELECTION OF EFFECTIVE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES FOR SUBJECTS OF THE RUSSIAN AGRO-INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX BASED ON FORECASTING TOOLS

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Abstract. *In modern conditions, the justified application of forecasting tools for the formation of effective innovative strategies for their development is of primary importance for the subjects of the Russian agro-industrial complex. This circumstance predetermines the high relevance of the topic of this work. Since the process of forming innovative development strategies and making investment decisions is associated with many alternative options and risk, there is a need to improve the methodology of portfolio investment and assess the investment qualities of the entire arsenal of investment portfolio strategies in order to justify the choice of the most optimal one. This article reveals the issues of forming effective innovative strategies for the development of subjects of the Russian agro-industrial complex based on forecasting the dynamics of crop yields using a system of hybrid models.*

Keywords: *profitability, risk, portfolio theory, investment tool, forecasting system of models.*

Introduction

Modern research in the field of mathematical support for financial management includes the development of innovative development strategies and tools to improve the efficiency of decision-making when managing investments in individual stock assets. This area includes methods of technical analysis (C. Lebeau, D.V. Lucas, A. Elder, etc.), applied regression analysis and time series analysis (N. Draper, G. Smith, J. Seber, J. Box, G. Jenkins, I. Fisher, etc.). Another area relates to the theory of portfolio investments (works by G. Markowitz [1], W. Sharpe [2], J. Tobin, R. Merton, R. Roll, etc.). These studies are based on the analysis

of the combined effect of investments in various investment instruments, taking into account their mutual influence. Despite the variety of works on improving investment mechanisms in financial markets, the problem of coordinating various approaches and creating a comprehensive investment system has not received due development.

In addition, the process of forming innovative development strategies and making investment decisions is associated with many alternative options and risks. Investors willing to invest money face the problem of adequate and objective risk assessment and investment prospects. The above circumstances have predetermined the need to improve the methodology of portfolio investment and assessment of the investment qualities of the entire arsenal of investment portfolio strategies in order to reasonably select the most optimal one in relation to the activities of business entities in the agro-industrial complex.

This article is devoted to the issues of forming effective innovative development strategies for business entities in the agro-industrial complex based on forecasting the dynamics of crop yields using a system of hybrid models.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to develop effective innovative strategies for the development of business entities in the agro-industrial complex and improve methods for forecasting crop yields. This goal determined the need to solve the following problems:

- to propose the most preferable mechanism for constructing a forecast of crop yields;
- to conduct a comparative testing of the proposed mechanisms for forecasting crop yields.

Materials and methods

Achieving the set goal required:

- a) assessing the forecasting capabilities of empirical models using information on exchange rate dynamics in stock markets;
- b) formulating the methodological foundations of multi-factor portfolio modeling;
- c) developing and verifying an arsenal of investment portfolio strategies synthesized on the basis of a hybrid system of models.

At the initial stage, a hybrid forecasting system is built based on the available historical data. Building a system of models is a two-stage procedure:

- 1) to assess the relationships between the investment instruments under study, a correlation analysis is carried out, and simultaneous regression equations are built:

$$y_i(k) = a_0 + \sum_{j=1}^m a_j y_j(k), j \neq i. \quad (1),$$

where y_i – investment instruments;
 m – number of investment instruments used;
 k – number of the year in which the research is conducted.

2) for each investment instrument, predictive models are synthesized, the initial form of which can be represented as follows:

$$y_i = a_0 + \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{t=1}^p a_{ji} y_j(k-t). \tag{2}$$

After completing the stage of constructing forecast models and checking their suitability (on q_2), the following options are possible:

1. There is not a single model in the system that is suitable for generating forecasts.

In this case, the current time interval (bar) is skipped, i.e. the investment portfolio is not formed in this time interval.

2. The synthesized system of empirical models according to the selected quality criteria is suitable in full.

In this case, the investment portfolio is built for the studied set of investment instruments.

3. Verification of the models showed that not all models are suitable for practical application.

In this case, unreliable prognostic models are replaced by corresponding simultaneous models. The system of models obtained in this way will be called hybrid, since it includes models of different structures (simultaneous and prognostic).

If several suitable empirical models are obtained for some investment instrument (instruments), then in this case the resulting profitability forecast is formed by combining the forecasts [3].

Next we move on to forming an investment portfolio (unique for each moment in time) k from q_3). Into the portfolio at each step of the rolling verification from the initial number m investment instruments, only those for which positive yield values were obtained according to the prognostic models are included in the consideration [4]. For the convenience of further presentation, the adjusted number of investment instruments will again be designated – m . Let’s write down the generally accepted restrictions: ($w_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, m,$), where w_i – weight i-ro investment instrument.

$$\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1. \tag{3}$$

We will determine the weights of investment instruments proportionally to the predicted value of profitability obtained using predictive models. For this purpose, we find the sum of the profitability forecasts:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^m D(x)_i. \tag{4}$$

Then the weights of investment instruments can be determined from the expression:

$$w_i = \frac{D(x)_i}{S}. \quad (5).$$

Thus, we obtain the optimal investment portfolio for the current moment in time – for the k -th year. Having processed all time intervals from q_3 , we obtain a series of points $(D(x), R_s)$, where R_s is the risk level, according to which we construct the “Risk-Profit” model. [4].

The proposed approach was tested for the formation of investment strategies in global stock markets [5]. Based on data on the yield of treasury bills, common stocks, long-term government and corporate bonds and on changes in the consumer price index for 1986÷2013, simultaneous and predictive models were built. Data for 2014÷2023 were reserved for the final testing of the approach.

1. Correlation analysis showed that the yield on government and corporate bonds correlates very closely with each other.
2. Models were obtained for forecasting:
 - a) yield on treasury bills. Forecast lead time is one year;
 - b) changes in the consumer price index, which reflects the inflation rate in the USA.
3. In accordance with the portfolio theory, a scatter diagram was constructed based on the calculated estimates of expected yield and risk level (for 2013 (see Fig)).

The results obtained are fully consistent with generally accepted concepts: the minimum value for expected yield and risk over the above time interval was shown by treasury bills, and the maximum by ordinary shares, with bonds of both types occupying an intermediate value.

The “Risk-Yield” model has the following form:

$$Dx = 0,64R_s; R^2 = 0,93. \quad (6),$$

where Dx – profit, R_s – risk.

Figure. Scatterplot for 2013.

The synthesized model of profitability forecast was tested on data for 2014–2023.

The forecast values of yield on treasury bills in the period under consideration are positive and correlate with historical data at a satisfactory level. $r = 0,67$. Here r is the correlation coefficient.

Thus, both studied approaches based on portfolio analysis and based on a hybrid system of models consistently recommend purchasing treasury bills.

Results and discussion

Based on the methods and materials described above, methodological recommendations for forecasting crop yields were developed. Their direct implementation in the practical activities of business entities in the agro-industrial complex will contribute to the formation of effective innovative strategies for their development.

The models presented below were built on statistical data on the dynamics of crop yields for a number of agricultural crops for the period from 2014 to 2023 with a time interval of one year [4].

The original sample of statistical data is divided chronologically into two non-overlapping subsamples: educational – q_1 and verification – q_2 . The input variables used are the prices of the crops under study: grains and legumes (Y), sugar beets (S), sunflower (P), potatoes (Kr) and vegetables (O).

The training subsample is used to synthesize predictive models of optimal complexity. Namely, on q_1 unknown coefficients of candidate models are found, then the constructed models are verified for the quality of the forecast q_2 .

Initially, to assess the relationship between the above-mentioned agricultural crops, a correlation analysis was conducted, from which it follows that the dynamics of the yield of all the studied crops closely correlate with each other, with the exception of the yield of potatoes.

The formation of a hybrid system of prognostic models is carried out in two stages.

At the first stage, forecasting models were developed.

Following E. Harvey [7] and K. Dougherty [3], a system of simultaneous forecasting models was built for the studied crops. Thus, for forecasting the yield of grain and legumes, a simultaneous model in general can be represented as follows:

$$Y(k) = a(0) + a(1) \times S(k) + a(2) \times P(k) + a(3) \times Kr(k) + a(4) \times O(k) \quad (7),$$

where k – time period number.

This formulation of the forecasting problem, in the opinion of the authors, seems quite reasonable, since the studied agricultural crops (in the general sense) function “in the same” environment and, therefore, can demonstrate stable statistical relationships. The presence of such relationships, in turn, allows us to synthesize models suitable for forecasting.

For each agricultural crop, models of the type presented above were constructed. For this, it was necessary to identify unknown coefficients and exclude from consideration those terms from the original structure for which the errors of the coefficients calculated with a confidence level of 95% turned out to be greater than the moduli of the coefficients themselves.

Then, having a certain set of price values for sugar beet, sunflower, potato and vegetables that do not belong to the training sample q_1 , not only was the suitability of the model tested, but also the predicted values of the yield of grain and leguminous crops were calculated.

Thus, models of this type (7) allow:

- 1) to quantitatively assess the interdependencies between the dynamics of the yield of the agricultural crops under consideration;
- 2) get an answer to the “what-if” question, i.e. calculate some scenarios for further developments.

The obtained models, based on the known values of the right-hand sides, allow us to calculate the corresponding values of grains and legumes, sugar beets, sunflowers and vegetables. An exception is the model for predicting potato yields, since its quality criterion does not meet the necessary requirements ($R^2 = 0.50$). In this regard, we will call the resulting system a weakly coupled system of simultaneous equations.

At the second stage, prognostic models of optimal complexity were developed.

For a more complete picture of the dynamics of crop yield, auto- and cross-correlation analysis was carried out for all studied agricultural crops with lags of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. The conducted correlation analysis showed that the order of the autoregressive equation is $p < 4$.

In general, models were constructed with lags of 1-3 years for the input variables $Y(k)$, $S(k)$, $P(k)$, $Kr(k)$, $O(k)$, starting with the equation:

$$Y(k) = a(0) + a(1) \times Y(k-1) + a(2) \times Y(k-2) + a(3) \times Y(k-3) + a(4) \times S(k-1) + a(5) \times S(k-2) + a(6) \times S(k-3) + a(7) \times P(k-1) + a(8) \times P(k-2) + a(9) \times P(k-3) + a(10) \times Kr(k-1) + a(11) \times Kr(k-2) + a(12) \times Kr(k-3) + a(13) \times O(k-1) + a(14) \times O(k-2) + a(15) \times O(k-3) \quad (8)$$

Not all presented models are suitable for direct application in practice. The following forecast models meet the requirements of practice: yield of grain and leguminous crops, sunflower and vegetables. The model for forecasting the yield of sugar beet cannot be used directly, since the quality criterion of this model is $R^2 = 0.64$.

To improve the efficiency of investment decisions, we will replace the forecast equation with the previously obtained simultaneous equation, which has a significantly higher value of the determination coefficient. Thus, it is finally recommended to use a hybrid system of models containing both simultaneous models

and forecast models for the practical development of innovative strategies for the development of business entities in the agro-industrial complex. In general, the structure of such an equation (for forecasting the yield of grain and leguminous crops) can be presented in the following form:

$$Y(k) = a(0) + a(1) \times Y(k-1) + a(2) \times Y(k-2) + a(3) \times Y(k-3) + a(4) \times S(k-1) + a(5) \times S(k-2) + a(6) \times S(k-3) + a(7) \times P(k-1) + a(8) \times P(k-2) + a(9) \times P(k-3) + a(10) \times Kr(k-1) + a(11) \times Kr(k-2) + a(12) \times Kr(k-3) + a(13) \times O(k-1) + a(14) \times O(k-2) + a(15) \times O(k-3) + a(16) \times S(k) + a(17) \times P(k) + a(18) \times Kr(k) + a(19) \times O(k) \quad (9).$$

In the problem under consideration, it was not possible to synthesize a model for forecasting the dynamics of potato yield. Consequently, further investment analysis in the time interval under consideration will be carried out on a truncated list of crops: grain and legumes, sunflower, sugar beet and vegetables. If several suitable models are obtained for a certain crop, then in this case the resulting yield forecast is formed by combining the forecasts.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained in the course of the conducted research, the following conclusions can be formulated:

1. In the process of forming innovative development strategies and making investment decisions, there is a need to choose the most optimal option from a variety of alternatives. This, in turn, implies further improvement of the methodology of portfolio investment and assessment of the quality of options for innovative development strategies based on specialized tools for forecasting the dynamics of agricultural crop yields.

2. As such a tool, a hybrid forecasting system is proposed, which has its own algorithm for constructing using statistical data for certain time periods.

3. The introduction of hybrid systems of production management models obtained in the course of the conducted research into the practical activities of economic entities of the agro-industrial complex can be used to improve the development of innovative strategies for their development.

References

1. Markovitz H.M. *Portfolio selection. J. of Finance. 1952. Vol. 7. № 1. Pp. 77-91.*
2. Sharpe W., Alexander G., Bailey J. *Investments. – M.: INFRA-M, 2016. – 1040 p.*
3. Gertsekovich D.A. *Quantitative methods for analyzing financial markets. – Irkutsk: Irkutsk State University Publishing House, 2008. – 335 p.*

4. Gertsekovich D.A., Podlinyaev O.L., Noak N.V. *Optimization of parameters and verification of the investment portfolio of economic entities in the framework of forming their development strategies. // Proceedings of the Twentieth All-Russian Symposium "Strategic Planning and Enterprise Development". Section 2. Models and methods for developing an enterprise strategy, Moscow, April 9-10, 2019. Moscow: Central Economics and Mathematics Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences. P. 228-230.*

5. Dougherty K. *Introduction to Econometrics*. – M.: INFRA-M, 1997. – 402 p.

6. *Investments in Russia. 2023: Statistical Digest*. – M.: Rosstat, 2023. – 229 p.

7. Harvey Andrew C. *The Econometric Analysis of Time Series. LSE handbooks in economics London School of Economics handbooks in economic analysis: MIT Press 1990*. – 387 p.